

Studies on Isoxazolones. Part II. Cu(II), Co(II) and UO₂(II) Chelates of Dimethyl Diisoxazolone

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Metal chelates of dimethyl diisoxazolone (R_mH) with Cu(II), Co(II) and UO₂(II) have been isolated. Magnetic susceptibilities of Cu(II) and Co(II) chelates have been measured. Electronic and ir spectral data of the ligand R_mH and its metal chelates have been recorded and discussed.

DIMETHYL diisoxazolone¹ (R_mH) forms stable complexes with Cu(II), Co(II) and UO₂(II) which have been isolated. All the isolated chelates of R_mH are coloured and hydrated. They are Cu(R_m)₂·4H₂O, Co(R_m)₂·6H₂O and UO₂(R_m)₂·2H₂O. Various physicochemical properties of the ligand R_mH and its metal derivatives have been studied.

Experimental

The ligand R_mH was prepared and purified following usual procedure^{1, 2}. The metal derivatives were prepared as stated below.

Cu(R_m)₂·4H₂O :

To an aqueous solution of copper acetate (1 mole), an ethanolic solution of R_mH (2 moles) was added with stirring. An olive green compound separated (pH ≈ 3.5-4.0) which was subsequently filtered, washed with water thoroughly, finally with ethanol and dried in air. The compound is insoluble in water, soluble in methanol but sparingly so in ethanol. [Found : Cu, 12.91 ; N, 11.34 ; Cu (R_m)₂·4H₂O requires Cu, 12.87 ; N, 11.35%].

The compound on heating at 110° for 2 hr showed a loss in weight corresponded to four molecules of water and the colour of the compound was changed from green to red. [Found : Loss, 14.50 ; calc. for 4 molecules of water, 14.57%].

Co(R_m)₂·6H₂O :

To an aqueous solution of cobalt acetate (1 mole), a hot aqueous ethanolic solution of R_mH (2 moles) was added and the mixture was digested on water bath for about two hrs and then left overnight at room temperature. An orange yellow crystalline precipitate appeared (pH ≈ 4.0), which was thoroughly washed with water, finally with ethanol and air-dried. The compound is insoluble in water, soluble in methanol and sparingly so in ethanol. Found : Co, 11.49 ; N, 10.58 ; Co(R_m)₂·6H₂O requires Co, 11.22 ; N, 10.66%].

The compound on heating at 110° for 2 hr showed a loss in weight corresponded to six molecules of water and the colour of the compound was changed from orange yellow to purple [Found : loss, 19.75 ; calc. for 6 molecules of water, 20.57%].

UO₂(R_m)₂·2H₂O :

An ethanolic solution of R_mH (2 moles) was added to an aqueous solution of uranyl acetate (1 mole) with stirring. An orange coloured crystalline precipitate appeared (pH ≈ 3.5-4.0), which was washed thoroughly with water, finally with ethanol and air-dried. The compound is insoluble in water, soluble in methanol and sparingly so in ethanol. [Found : U, 35.83 ; N, 8.50 ; UO₂(R_m)₂·2H₂O requires U, 35.84 ; N, 8.44%]. The compound on heating at 140° showed neither any loss in weight nor any change in colour.

Magnetic moments of the Cu(II) and Co(II) complexes have been determined at room temperature and μ_{eff} values after diamagnetic corrections³ are recorded in Table 1.

Electronic absorption spectra of the metal chelates of R_mH have been recorded in a number of solvents as well as in mull by means of UVISPEK spectrophotometer at room temperature (25°). Data are stated in Table 1. In the case of mull spectra, O. D. values are noted in arbitrary units. Electronic spectral data of R_mH are also included in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF R_mH AND ITS METAL CHELATES AND MAGNETIC DATA OF $Cu(II)$ AND $Co(II)$ CHELATES.

Species	λ_{max}^{MeOH} (nm)	log ϵ	λ_{max}^{DMF} (nm)	log ϵ	λ_{max}^{Mull} (nm)	O.D.	Temperature °K	U_{eff} (BM)
$R_mH \cdot H_2O$	290	4.76	308	3.23				
	257	4.38	255	3.40				
	212	4.23	214	3.99				
$Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$	780	2.13	740	1.99	660	0.760	294	1.87
	—	—	530	2.66	—	—		
	485-80	2.63	470	2.84	430	1.335		
	291	4.56	307	4.80				
$Co(R_m)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	259	4.24	255	4.31			303	4.67
	880	0.69	—	—	—	—		
	680	1.06	—	—	675(sh)	0.480		
	588	1.25	630-10	0.44	615	0.550		
	520	1.51	520	1.36	550(sh)	0.570		
	289	4.60	—	—	382	1.060		
$UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	258	4.16	—	—				
	370	2.88	—	—	430(sh)	1.822		
	290.5	4.67	307	4.07				
	256	4.34	267	4.59				
	212.5	4.71	251	4.41				

I. R. spectra of $R_mH \cdot H_2O$ and its metal chelates have been recorded in KBr matrices and tentative assignments^{4,5} of some important vibrations have been made. Data are stated in Table 2.

Conductance measurements of the ligand R_mH and its $UO_2(II)$ chelate in methanolic solution were made with a Phillips RCL Bridge PP 9030. Results are stated in Table 3.

TABLE 2—I. R. SPECTRAL DATA OF $R_mH \cdot H_2O$ AND ITS METAL CHELATES IN KBr MATRICES

Frequencies Cm^{-1}					Tentative Assignments
$R_mH \cdot H_2O$	$Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$	$Co(R_m)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	$UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$		
3472(b st)	3390(b st)	3448(b st)	3448(b m)		N-H, O-H or H-bonded H_2O
3334(Sp St)					C=O stretches
1666(b St)	—	—	—		C=N stretches
1626(b St)	1626(Sp w) 1620(Sp St)	1613(b st)	1626(b St)		
1562(b m)	1562(Sh m)	1543(Sp St)	1562(Sh, St)		Lattice or coordinated water
1361(b m)	—	—	—		O-H bending
1064(Sp St)	1031(Sh St)	1031(Sp St)	1031(Sp w)		N-O stretches
931(Sp m)	961(Sh m)	943(Sp w)	943(Sp St)		Heterocyclic breathing modes
829(Sp m)	816(Sp m)	792(Sp w)	790(Sp w)		
765(b St)	778(b m)	769(Sp w)	752(b w)		

Sp—Sharp; b—broad; Sh—Shoulder; St—Strong; m—medium; w—weak.

TABLE 3—CONDUCTANCE DATA OF $R_mH \cdot H_2O$ AND $UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ IN METHANOLIC SOLUTION TEMPERATURE 25°

Square root of concentrations in mols per litre \sqrt{C}		0.125	0.088	0.062	0.044	0.031	0.022	0.016	0.011
Molar conductance in moles cm^2	$R_mH \cdot H_2O$	2.21	3.07	4.19	5.63	7.55	9.21	17.15	25.60
	$UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	11.84	14.17	22.41	29.88	51.35	69.85	94.61	149.9

Discussion

All the isolated complex compounds of R_mH are coloured and hydrated. On dehydration, the loss of 4 and 6 molecules of water from $Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ and $Co(R_m)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ respectively have resulted in changes of colour. The water molecules are probably involved in crystal formation. Both of them, however, have regained their original colour on exposure to atmosphere—evidently due to absorption of moisture from air. But $UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ have showed no loss of water on heating even at 140° and no change of colour has been perceived. The two water molecules probably occupy the coordination positions.

The ligand R_mH and its uranyl complex are insoluble in water. So their electrical conductance have been measured in methanolic solution. Data indicate that R_mH is a weak electrolyte (acid) and $UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ is an electrolyte of moderate strength. The electrical conductance values $7.55-25.60 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ of the ligand R_mH denote it to be a uni-univalent weak acid. Conductance values $29.88-51.35 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ and the higher value $149.9 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ of $UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ are in the range expected for uni-univalent electrolyte at the beginning and bi-univalent electrolyte finally⁶. The ligand R_mH is a weak monobasic acid of moderate strength which is also indicated by its pK_a value—found to be 2.40 at 27° in (1:1) water-methanol².

The electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes generally show characteristic band in the region $900-600 \text{ nm}$ ⁷. The absorption maximum of $Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ in mull is found at 660 nm which is shifted to 740 nm in DMF and to 780 nm in methanol. The ϵ_{max} values in both the solvents support distorted octahedral structure⁸. The red shift of the d-d band of $Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ indicate that methanol is a more strongly coordinating axial ligand than DMF and it is clear that the position of this band is a useful indication of the degree of tetragonal distortion⁹ supporting a square planar or much greater tetragonally distorted structure for the Cu(II) complex. The Co(II) complex shows absorption bands in methanolic solution at $880, 588$ and 520 nm due to known transitions for octahedral complexes, i. e. from ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state to ${}^2E_g, {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ states respectively. In DMF the absorption bands are observed at $630-610$ and 520 nm and in mull at 615 and 550 nm . Evidently they are due to known transitions for octahedral complexes i. e. from ${}^4T_{1g}$ ground state to ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $T_{1g}(P)$ states respectively. Thus the absorption spectra of $Co(R_m)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ support a distorted octahedral structure^{7,10}. Regarding the electronic spectra of $UO_2(II)$ complexes little of known, Jorgensen's study¹¹ on the absorption spectra of uranyl ion using $UO_2(ClO_4)_2$ in $HClO_4$ medium shows two groups of bands of low extinctions in the range $487-380 \text{ nm}$ and $351-310 \text{ nm}$. He has ascribed these bands to transfer an odd electron from the ligands to the empty 5f shell of the central ion. In the present investigation of $UO_2(R_m)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, the absorption band found at 370 nm in methanol may be due to uranyl ion.

The magnetic data are often useful in the characterisation of complexes^{3,12}. Magnetic moment value

of $Cu(R_m)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ has been found to be 1.87 BM, suggesting square planar or distorted octahedral configuration. Magnetic moment value of $Co(R_m)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ has been found to be 4.67 BM. The high spin octahedral Co(II) compounds have magnetic moments ranging from 4.7 to 5.2 BM⁷. In the present case the value of 4.67 BM may be expected for a high spin octahedral complex. Its electronic spectra also support an octahedral structure which has already been stated.

The ir spectra of $R_mH \cdot H_2O$ and its metal chelates show bands at $3472-3390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of water molecules in the ligand as well as in its metal complexes. Band at $1562-1543 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand and its metal chelates shows the presence of lattice or coordinated water. The C=O stretch at 1666 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligand R_mH disappears on complex formation indicating that the enolised form of R_mH takes part in complex formation. The band at 1361 cm^{-1} found in the spectra of the ligand which is due to O—H bending, is absent in its complexes with Cu(II), Co(II) and $UO_2(II)$. The ir spectral data show shifts in N—O stretching frequency at 1064 cm^{-1} in the ligand (R_mH) to lower frequency 1031 cm^{-1} in the complexes. Thus chelation takes place through —OH by proton displacement and through O of N—O with the formation of M—O bonds.

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